

USING CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT SYSTEM TO IMPROVE ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE – EXPLORATORY STUDY ON ROMANIAN SMES

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Abstract

Purpose – This aim of this research is to understand how the dynamics of CRM usage have changed SMEs practices and influenced their organizational performance. Following a literature review to establish the key issues in the field, this research study will develop an exploratory framework.

Methodology/approach - The elements of influence for the formation of CRM practices within companies have been examined from different theoretical points of view and received significant attention. Theories that have been used to understand the elements of CRM practices include the theory of resource-based visualization (RBV) and the theory of marketing relationships (RMT). In this study, CRM resources are classified as technological CRM resources, knowledge management and customer orientation. The survey questions were stated as closed questions, using the Likert scale (with values from 1 to 7) as an answer.

Findings – The study proposed analyzes the the impact of CRM usage on SMEs performance. Using statistical data, technical information and case studies, through quantitative and qualitative analysis, the research conducted identifies the current state of CRM usage. Based on this research, this research defines CRM as a core business strategy for providing information through the use of information technology tools to establish long-term customer relationships. It is impossible for organizations to have all the necessary resources to remain competitive without having a close relationship with customers.

Research limitations/implications – Respondents were especially young people whose behavior could differ somewhat from the population average. Another limitation was that the Romanian sample contained many full-time workers. However, many of the students in Romania work full time, which makes the two samples compatible.

Practical implications – This study will be added to the relatively limited empirical research, based on Customer Relationship Management system usage. More than that, it adds to the limited number of empirical studies by exploring the impact of CRM system adoption on the organizational performance of small and medium business enterprises.

Originality/value – The significant effect that influences the organizational performance toward using CRM system is represented by organizational capability had the most important influence.

Key words: Customer Relationship Management system, SMEs performance, business digitalization.

Introduction

As small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are considered to be the main driver of global economic development, they have attracted enough attention from researchers. This interest stems from the fact that innovation, especially in information technology, depends substantially on the potential of small and medium-sized enterprises. The nature of business in all countries is changing fast and developing countries are upgrading their infrastructure and capitalize the Internet. There are problems associated with this new interactive media such as security and technological problems, lack of trust, face-to-face communications lack or privacy issues. Moreover, the changing can mean that SMEs may not fully understand the potentials of a digital market place since the Internet and electronic communication is rapidly changing traditional marketing practices and techniques.

There is an urgent need to understand the impact of CRM system usage on customer and business market performance. To address SMEs competitive needs, companies need to carry out research to investigate the antecedents for successful implementation of CRM system. In the context of the economic and trade transformations specific to the 21st century, digitalisation among SMEs and e-commerce have a strategic, defining role in modernizing the multilateral trading system. It can be said that digitalization is part of the life of SMEs and brings efficiency in business, production and marketing and sales processes. It can help strengthen energy efficiency, resource efficiency, innovation, sustainability and competitiveness. Romania needs an innovative ICT industry and an upgrade of the digital innovation capacity of all industries.

Theoretical background

Small and medium enterprises - theoretical methodological aspects

The Micro, Small and Medium-sized Enterprise (SME) category consists of enterprises that employ less than 250 people and have a net annual turnover of up to EUR 50 million and / or have total assets of up to EUR 43 million. SMEs importance began to appear especially in the 1970s, and in the 1980s they experienced a significant expansion, their share increasing significantly both in Europe and in the United States and Japan. Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are the basic structure of the economy and the main source of economic growth in both developed and least developed countries in Europe. These are very important at the governmental level due to their potential to provide jobs for the population. However, the gaps between the regions are still important both in Romania and in the Member States of the European Union. In Romania, the SME sector represents approximately 99.7% of the business population, and in Europe 99.8%. 93% of non-financial firms are micro-enterprises with up to 10 employees (Masculu & Mureşan, 2019).

The importance of SMEs in Romania is based on the following facts: it is the supply for most products and services needed by the population of a country, they are the main generating values in any country, they provide jobs for most people and their performance affects the status and performance of all countries. the living standard of the population (Nicolescu & Nicolescu, 2008).

CRM system and organization performance

CRM is a useful system for generating, storing, representing, reproducing and translating information. It is adopted to manage customer interactions or relationships and to improve the company's understanding of consumer profiles (Gupte, 2011). The general process of developing and maintaining profitable communication with the customer is by delivering or presenting a higher value for the customer and obtaining his satisfaction. Gamson considers CRM as a necessary rule for those organizations that need development and growth, in which the identification of the key dimensions of CRM is very important. Regarding large-scale studies in CRM, there are several classifications, the most important of which are presented below in Table 1.

Table 1. Classification of CRM-related system factors

Classification of CRM-related factors	Source
Operation, analysis, interaction	Berson et al.,1999
Data collection, storage, summary, display and application	Swift, 2001
Understanding customer behavior based on multiple viewing	Amrit, 2001
Internet support, customer support and market support	Ming&Chen, 2002
Organizational structure, knowledge management, value creation strategy, information technology, culture, individuals, process, customer interaction	Lindgreen, 2004
Philosophy, capacity and technology	Zablah et al., 2004
Excellent management, internal market, management knowledge and IT business	Chen, Q., Chen, H, 2004

(source: Mozaheb et al., 2015, p.44)

Methodology

The elements of influence for the formation of CRM practices within companies have been examined from different theoretical points of view and received significant attention. Theories that have been used to understand the elements of CRM practices include the theory of resource-based visualization (RBV) (Halawi et al., 2005; Keramati et al., 2010) and the theory of marketing relationships (RMT). RBV provides an adequate multidimensional perspective on the application of CRM, as it seeks to link the performance of superior firms with the various resources that lead to a competitive advantage (Coltman, 2007).

In this study, CRM resources are classified as technological CRM resources, knowledge management and customer. RMT is met to promote the customer and supplier on an adverse, stimulating reaction to marketing feedback (Rese, 2006). This study incorporates RBV and RMT theories to understand how Romanian SMEs form CRM practices and organizational performance. From this theory results a set of hypotheses that have been expressed in research:

H1: Customer orientation is positively related to organizational performance.

H2: Organizational capability is positively related to organizational performance.

H3: Technological resources are positively related to organizational performance.

H4: The knowledge management of the organization is positively related to the organizational performance (Mohammad, 2013).

The data collection was carried out between March and May 2020 by the method of the questionnaire, which has 27 questions, and at the end of the session allocated to complete the questionnaire, a total number of 65 respondents was registered. The significance level of 5% will be used as a threshold for testing research proposals. The sample sample will be based on the stratified sample that would have formed from the small and medium-sized companies, defined as a sample frame.

Results

Table 2 presents some of the demographics of the respondents. Descriptive statistics show a fairly young and well-educated population, about 95% of respondents being under the age of forty, while 70% of them have at least a university degree. In terms of gender, the population is not evenly divided between male and female respondents. Most respondents are in the female category, which are 41 people (63%), and men the difference of 24 people (37%).

Table 2. Demographic statistics

	Attribute	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Female	41	63.1
	Male	24	36.9
Age	18-23 years	28	43.1
	24-30 years	29	44.6
	31-37 years	5	7.7
	38-45 years	2	3.1
	More than 45 years	1	1.5
Education level	Postgraduate studies	16	24.6
	University studies	46	70.8
	Others	3	4.6

According to Table 3, the value of the correlation coefficient for the 17 variables structured in 5 factors in this study ranged from .240 to .823. The Cronbach Alpha coefficient is used to study the internal consistency of the items in a questionnaire or can be used as a method to reduce some items. The not-too-distant values produced here (.917 vs. .915) indicate that the means and variances in the original scales do not differ much, and therefore standardization does not make much of a difference in Alpha. In this case, the Cronbach Alpha value is .917, which indicates a very good to excellent value. Moreover, it indicates a fairly high degree of internal coherence with regard to the specific sample.

Table 3. Cronbach Alpha analysis

Cronbach Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.917	.915	17

A correlation is often called a bivariate correlation to designate a simple correlation between two variables (Table 4), as opposed to relationships between more than two variables, as is frequently observed in multiple regression analyzes or modeling of structural equations. A correlation is also often called the Pearson product-moment correlation or Pearson r. Karl S. Pearson is credited with the formula from which these correlations are calculated. The highest positive relationship existed between Organizational Performance and Organizational Capability ($r = .713$, $\text{Sig} = .000$), followed by the link between Organizational Capability and Information Technology ($r = .695$, $\text{Sig} = .000$). These values indicate a positive relationship for the connection between the factors Organization Performance and Organizational Capability, respectively Organizational Capability and Information Technology.

Table 4. Pearson Correlation Matrix

Factors		OC	CO	TI	MC	PO
OC	Pearson Correlation	1	.510**	.466**	.483	.426**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
CO	Pearson Correlation	.510**	1	.695**	.595**	.713
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
TI	Pearson Correlation	.466**	.695**	1	.658**	.614**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
MC	Pearson Correlation	.483**	.595**	.658**	1**	.576**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
PO	Pearson Correlation	.426**	.713**	.614**	.576**	1**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	

As can be seen in Table 5, the linear regression coefficient $R = 0.743$, which indicates that there is a correlation between the dependent and the independent variables. Regarding variability, the value of $R^2 = 0.552$ or 55.2% which explains the variability within the population (this means that 55.2% of the population in the sample agree with the correlation between the given variables).

Table 5. Linear Regression

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.743 ^a	.552	.523	.83589

From table 6 respondents answers, more than half of them (88%) work in private companies, and 12% of respondents in state companies.

Table 6. Company type

The company you work for is:	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Micro enterprise	14	21.5
Small business	23	35.3
Medium enterprise	28	43.0
private	57	87.7
Of the state	8	12.3

In Table 7, the answers to the question regarding the years since the company operates, most companies have more than 15 years on the market (49%), followed by those between 7 and 15 years (19%) , and the difference of 33% is cumulated by those aged between 3 and 7 years (15%) and less than 3 years (17%).

Table 7. Company age

How many years has the company been established?	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Between 3 and 7 years	10	15.4
Between 7 and 15 years	12	18.5
More than 15 years	32	49.2
Less than 3 years	11	16.9

The validity of the acceptability model was verified, using the modeling of structural equations, adapting the model to the sampled sample (shown in figure 1) and then validation / invalidation of hypotheses, taking into account the coefficient β and standard error, analyzed using SPSS AMOS program, demonstrated in table 8.

Figure 1. Model on organizational performance in SMEs in Romania, resulting from research

Table 8. Validation / Invalidation of Hypotheses

Hypotheses	β Coefficient	Standard Error	Hypothesis Validation / Invalidation
H1: Customer orientation is positively related to organizational performance.	.037	.186	VALIDATE
H2: Organizational capability is positively related to organizational performance.	.475	.118	VALIDATE
H3: Technological resources are positively related to organizational performance.	.129	.117	VALIDATE
H4: The knowledge management of the organization is positively related to the organizational performance.	.191	.127	VALIDATE

Discussion and conclusions

However, another very important aspect is that Romania is in the queue for European charts that measure the progress of EU countries towards a digital economy and society. Romania, which is a destination for IT services and products, which has very relevant players on the regional and global market, seems to be waiting between two realities: that of innovative industries and the preservation of digitalization. The results indicated that all variables, except customer orientation, significantly affected the organizational performance of SMEs following the adoption and use of the CRM system. Among them, organizational capability had the most important influence.

Based on this research defines CRM as a core business strategy for providing information through the use of information technology tools to establish long-term customer relationships. It is impossible for organizations to have all the necessary sources to remain competitive without having a close relationship with customers. Therefore, it is essential for organizations to implement CRM resources to develop strong CRM capabilities, subsequently improving the performance of companies.

Thus, by managing and maintaining CRM more efficiently, SMEs can satisfy their customers and achieve operational performance. On the other hand, the study found a positive and significant influence of only three dimensions of CRM (ie customer orientation, organizational capability and knowledge management) on learning and growth,

Limitations

This study had some limitations, mainly in terms of sampling and technologies examined. Respondents were especially young people whose behavior could differ somewhat from the population average. The other limitation was that the Romanian sample contained many full-time workers. However, many of the students in Romania work full time, which makes the two samples compatible. The consumers examined use the system, even if they do not fully accept it. This research is an exploratory one, designed to identify the organizational performance according to the adoption rate of Customer Relationship Management in Small and Medium Enterprises in Romania. The research is relevant to understanding the experience of sample respondents, but is still unrepresentative for CRM solution users.

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